

Effect of zinc on N, P, K and Zn concentration, uptake and Zn efficiency in rice

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ABSTRACT

An experiment was carried out in Gazipur, Bangladesh to investigate the response of agronomical, physiological, apparent recovery, utilization zinc use efficiency, zinc concentration in endosperm and yield of rice to zinc. The design of experiment was Randomized Complete Block with three replications included zinc fertilizer level (0, 10 and 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ as H₂O₅SZn) and three rice varieties BRRIdhan56, BRRIdhan57 and BRRIdhan62. 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ significantly increased the yield and yield contributing characters in BRRIdhan56 and BRRIdhan57 and 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRRIdhan 62. The highest Zn content in endosperm (39.85 ppm) was recorded at 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRRIdhan62 and the lowest (16.27 ppm) at 0 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRRIdhan57. The highest agronomic, physiological, apparent recovery and utilization efficiency were recorded at 10 kg Znha⁻¹ and the lowest at 20 kg Znha⁻¹. It was revealed that the rice varieties BRRIdhan56, BRRIdhan57 responded to the application of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹, while BRRIdhan62 to 20 kg Znha⁻¹. So, to obtain the highest yield to ensure satisfactory zinc content in BRRIdhan56, BRRIdhan57 with the most zinc use efficiency and avoid of environmental pollution, use of 10 kg Znha⁻¹ while 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ to BRRIdhan62.

INTRODUCTION

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) belongs to the family of Graminae is the main staple food of around half of the world's population. Reports showed that 30% soils in the world exhibit zinc deficiency to different extent and more than two billion people can't be supplied with sufficient zinc (Cakmak et al., 2008). Zinc deficiency is prevalent worldwide in temperate and tropical climates (Slaton, 2005). Today, increasing grain Zn concentration of rice represents an important challenge to be met by using agricultural tools such as breeding and fertilization. Zinc concentrations of both polished and unpolished rice are inherently too low to meet human demands for Zn. In South and Southeast Asia, over half a billion people are estimated to be at risk from inadequate Zn intake (Hotz and Brown, 2004), and the well-known high incidence and severity of childhood infectious diseases in those regions are commonly associated with Zn deficiency (Black et al., 2008). The optimum dietary intake for human adults is 15 mg Zn day⁻¹. Minimum dietary intake of Zn may cause deficiency and the human body will suffer from hair and memory loss, skin problems and weakness in body muscles, infertility. During pregnancy unsatisfactory intake of Zn also causes stunted brain development of the foetus. The critical index of effective Zn in the soil suitable for rice growth is 1.5 mg kg⁻¹ (Xu, 2003). In a screening study including about 1,000 genotypes, it has been found that there is a four-fold range of rice grain Zn concentration among the rice varieties (e.g., 13.5–58.4 mg Zn kg⁻¹) (Graham et al., 1999).

This impressive genotypic variation has led to a suggestion that such substantial genetic potential for Zn concentration in rice should be exploited through plant breeding (Bouis and Welch, 2010). High grain yield of rice can be achieved only through a proper combination of variety, agronomic practices, environment and optimum moisture for de-husking (Mtetwa et al., 2017). Zinc and copper are essential elements for several biochemical processes in plants (kumar et al., 2012). Agronomic zinc biofortification of rice is an important complement to genetic zinc biofortification. Application of Zn-containing fertilizers represents a quick and effective approach to biofortify rice grains with Zn an excellent complementary tool. Though excess Zinc uptake showed toxic effects appeared on leaves and stem of plant, shoot length, biomass and dry weight of tomato (Gautam et al., 2016). Zn declined antioxidative defense with respect to (protein, sugar, pro) The aim of this study was to evaluate the effects of the zinc level and rice varieties on the zinc efficiency components (agronomic, physiological, apparent recovery and utilization efficiency), and the amount of zinc concentration and uptake by plant, yield and yield components in order to determination of the most suitable variety and zinc level to get favorite yield, highest zinc concentration in endosperm and use efficiency.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In order to investigation the response of agronomical, physiological, apparent recovery and utilization zinc use efficiency zinc concentration in

endosperm and yield of rice to zinc, a field experiment was carried out in Agronomy Field Laboratory BSMRAU campus Gazipur during aman 2015. The experiment was factorial in the base of Randomized Complete Block Design with three replications. Factors included zinc fertilizer level (0, 10 and 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ as zinc sulphate monohydrate) and three rice varieties (BRRIdhan56, BRRIdhan57 and BRRIdhan 62). The unit plot size was (3m×4m). Row and hill spacing was (20×15) cm. To know the response of these varieties to zinc fertilizer application the variety BRRIdhan 62 standard check variety. According to soil analysis results, low available Zn (mg kg⁻¹ 0.67) during final land preparation farm yard manure was incorporated into the soil at the rate of 5 t ha⁻¹ fertilizer dose of 80 kg N ha⁻¹, 36 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹, 50 kg K ha⁻¹, 20 kg S ha⁻¹, respectively was applied. Nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and sulfur were applied in the form of urea, TSP, MoP and gypsum, respectively. Zinc fertilizer was applied after nine days of transplanting and it was incorporated into the soil. At physiological maturity, plant samples were partitioned into endosperm, bran, leaf and culm and dried. The samples were ground separately by a grinding machine to pass through a 20-mesh sieve. A sub-sample weighing 0.5 g was transferred into a dry clean 100 ml long narrow tube. A 10 ml of diacid mixture (HNO₃: HClO₄ in the ratio of 2:1) was added. The concentration of Zn was determined by thermo atomic absorption spectrophotometer and all the data were analyzed by utilizing statistical software statistix10.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of zinc on nitrogen content and uptake

The highest nitrogen 1.9% in endosperm was found at interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ with BRRIdhan 62 and the lowest of that 1.5% was obtained for interaction of control treatment in BRRIdhan57. The highest N 1.83% in bran was found at interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRRIdhan 62 and the lowest of that 1.45% was obtained interaction of control treatment in BRRIdhan57. The highest N content in leaf 0.59% was found at interaction of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ for BRRIdhan57 and the lowest of that 0.45% was observed under interaction of control treatment for BRRIdhan57. Nitrogen content in leaf varied due to application of Zn supplied from fertilizer, however this variation was not significant, but N content in leaf ranged from 0.625 to 0.768%, the highest value being in Zn treatment and the lowest in control. The highest N content in culm 0.72% was obtained for BRRIdhan 62 and the lowest of that 0.51% was obtained for BRRIdhan56. The highest N uptake in endosperm 53.14 kg ha⁻¹ was found at interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ with BRRIdhan56 and the lowest of that 37.04 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained interaction of control treatment in BRRIdhan56. The highest N uptake in bran 22.29 kg ha⁻¹ was found at interaction of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ with BRRIdhan56 and the lowest of that 15.44 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained in interaction of control treatment for BRRIdhan57. The highest N uptake in culm 17.64 kg ha⁻¹ was found at interaction of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ with BRRIdhan 62 and the lowest of that 8.84 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained interaction of control treatment in BRRIdhan56 (Table 1). Concentration of N in paddy

Table-1 Mean comparison of zinc fertilizer application on nitrogen partitioning in rice genotypes endosperm, bran, leaf and culm

Treatment	Nitrogen Content (%)				Nitrogen Uptake Kg ha ⁻¹				
	Endosperm	Bran	Leaf	Culm	Endosperm	Bran	Leaf	Culm	Total
Zinc fertilizer									
Control	1.58	1.54	0.48	0.55	43.47	15.43	13.60	12.13	84.63
10 kg ha ⁻¹	1.66	1.64	0.57	0.64	48.74	18.08	17.21	15.15	99.18
20 kg ha ⁻¹	1.64	1.69	0.54	0.62	45.48	17.35	15.07	14.52	92.42
LSD _(.05)	NS	0.09	0.03	0.07	4.08	1.09	1.07	1.40	2.79
Varieties									
BRRIdhan56	1.62	1.55	0.51	0.51	48.75	20.32	13.12	10.54	88.47
BRRIdhan57	1.53	1.55	0.52	0.55	38.67	17.07	12.88	12.22	79.18
BRRIdhan62	1.88	1.77	0.53	0.72	47.28	19.46	13.89	16.04	96.67
LSD _(.05)	0.10	0.08	NS	0.06	3.09	1.06	NS	1.30	4.43
Zinc × Variety									
Zn ₀ ×V ₁	1.58	1.48	0.48	0.46	48.11	19.30	12.30	8.84	82.66
Zn ₁₀ ×V ₁	1.67	1.63	0.58	0.56	53.14	22.29	15.79	12.07	98.20
Zn ₂₀ ×V ₁	1.54	1.55	0.48	0.52	45.00	19.38	11.27	10.71	84.54
Zn ₀ ×V ₂	1.50	1.45	0.45	0.48	37.35	15.44	10.84	10.49	70.86
Zn ₁₀ ×V ₂	1.51	1.56	0.59	0.59	41.61	18.40	16.08	13.98	90.52
Zn ₂₀ ×V ₂	1.51	1.66	0.52	0.57	37.04	17.37	11.71	12.19	76.16
Zn ₀ ×V ₃	1.76	1.71	0.48	0.68	41.98	17.52	11.67	14.07	85.23
Zn ₁₀ ×V ₃	1.86	1.75	0.53	0.72	48.44	19.58	13.76	16.40	98.18
Zn ₂₀ ×V ₃	1.90	1.83	0.58	0.75	51.43	21.29	16.23	17.64	106.59
LSD _(.05)	NS	NS	0.07	NS	5.34	1.83	1.84	NS	4.71
CV (%)	6.05	5.09	7.71	10.18	6.88	5.58	8.01	10.08	3.09

Table-2 Mean comparison of zinc fertilizer application on phosphorus partitioning in rice genotypes endosperm, bran, leaf and culm in rice

Treatment	Phosphorus Content (%)				Phosphorus Uptake Kg ha ⁻¹				
	Endosperm	Bran	Leaf	Culm	Endosperm	Bran	Leaf	Culm	Total
Zinc fertilizer									
Control	0.126	0.038	0.040	0.034	3.328	0.421	0.973	0.702	5.424
10 kg ha ⁻¹	0.135	0.037	0.043	0.029	3.872	0.453	1.145	0.666	6.136
20 kg ha ⁻¹	0.124	0.036	0.046	0.028	3.382	0.418	1.110	0.619	5.528
LSD _(.05)	0.005	NS	NS	0.005	0.134	NS	NS	NS	0.254
Varieties									
BRRIdhan56	0.135	0.037	0.037	0.031	4.120	0.484	0.938	0.644	6.185
BRRIdhan57	0.128	0.038	0.040	0.024	3.287	0.417	0.971	0.540	5.215
BRRIdhan62	0.123	0.034	0.051	0.036	3.174	0.391	1.320	0.803	5.688
LSD _(.05)	0.005	NS	0.008	0.005	0.134	NS	0.213	0.100	0.254
Zinc × Variety									
Zn ₀ ×V ₁	0.133	0.027	0.031	0.042	4.025	0.349	0.788	0.830	5.991
Zn ₁₀ ×V ₁	0.145	0.039	0.039	0.028	4.612	0.528	1.049	0.604	6.792
Zn ₂₀ ×V ₁	0.128	0.046	0.042	0.024	3.724	0.574	0.976	0.498	5.772
Zn ₀ ×V ₂	0.126	0.044	0.028	0.031	3.133	0.468	0.668	0.678	4.947
Zn ₁₀ ×V ₂	0.137	0.037	0.037	0.025	3.758	0.436	1.012	0.589	5.795
Zn ₂₀ ×V ₂	0.121	0.033	0.055	0.017	2.971	0.348	1.233	0.352	4.904
Zn ₀ ×V ₃	0.119	0.044	0.060	0.029	2.826	0.448	1.464	0.597	5.334
Zn ₁₀ ×V ₃	0.124	0.035	0.052	0.036	3.244	0.396	1.375	0.805	5.821
Zn ₂₀ ×V ₃	0.127	0.029	0.040	0.043	3.450	0.331	1.120	1.008	5.909
LSD _(.05)	0.009	0.013	0.013	0.008	0.233	0.152	0.369	0.173	0.440
CV (%)	3.94	19.61	18.04	14.93	3.81	20.43	19.83	15.06	4.46

Table-3 Mean comparison of zinc fertilizer application on nitrogen partitioning in rice genotypes endosperm, bran, leaf and culm

Treatment	Potassium Content (%)				Potassium Uptake Kg ha ⁻¹				Total
	Endosperm	Bran	Leaf	Culm	Endosperm	Bran	Leaf	Culm	
Zinc fertilizer									
Control	0.28	0.23	0.60	0.78	7.24	2.57	14.69	16.00	40.49
10 kg ha ⁻¹	0.30	0.25	0.66	0.88	8.44	3.02	17.79	19.96	49.21
20 kg ha ⁻¹	0.29	0.24	0.67	0.84	7.71	2.80	16.74	18.65	45.90
LSD _(.05)	NS	NS	0.07	NS	0.87	0.34	1.72	3.00	3.38
Genotypes									
BRRIdhan56	0.26	0.21	0.64	0.82	7.80	3.09	16.19	16.09	44.08
BRRIdhan57	0.28	0.24	0.61	0.76	7.24	2.67	14.91	16.80	41.62
BRRIdhan62	0.32	0.26	0.69	0.92	8.34	2.63	18.12	20.81	49.90
LSD _(.05)	0.04	NS	0.07	0.10	NS	0.34	1.72	3.00	3.38
Zinc × Variety									
Zn ₀ × V ₁	0.25	0.21	0.58	0.78	7.59	2.90	14.67	15.14	40.31
Zn ₁₀ × V ₁	0.27	0.25	0.67	0.90	8.72	3.37	18.37	19.39	49.86
Zn ₂₀ × V ₁	0.24	0.24	0.66	0.79	7.10	3.00	15.53	16.44	42.07
Zn ₀ × V ₂	0.27	0.23	0.60	0.71	6.71	2.46	14.31	15.32	38.81
Zn ₁₀ × V ₂	0.30	0.27	0.63	0.81	8.25	3.19	16.89	19.00	47.32
Zn ₂₀ × V ₂	0.28	0.23	0.61	0.75	6.75	2.37	13.53	16.09	38.74
Zn ₀ × V ₃	0.31	0.23	0.61	0.84	7.40	2.35	15.08	17.52	42.35
Zn ₁₀ × V ₃	0.32	0.22	0.69	0.94	8.35	2.50	18.11	21.49	50.45
Zn ₂₀ × V ₃	0.34	0.26	0.75	0.99	9.28	3.02	21.16	23.42	56.88
LSD _(.05)	NS	NS	0.13	NS	NS	0.59	2.97	NS	5.85
CV (%)	12.70	12.5	11.41	11.86	11.21	12.14	10.47	16.51	7.48

Table-4 Mean comparison of zinc fertilizer application on nitrogen partitioning in rice genotypes endosperm, bran, leaf and culm

Treatment	Zinc Content (ppm)				Zinc Uptake Kg ha ⁻¹				Total
	Endosperm	Bran	Leaf	Culm	Endosperm	Bran	Leaf	Culm	
Zinc fertilizer									
Control	17.51	34.06	39.24	66.44	0.046	0.038	0.097	0.137	0.318
10 kg ha ⁻¹	26.11	41.67	50.66	81.34	0.074	0.051	0.136	0.184	0.445
20 kg ha ⁻¹	33.45	51.82	61.78	90.29	0.090	0.060	0.152	0.198	0.500
LSD _(.05)	1.30	2.87	2.66	3.97	0.004	0.004	0.008	0.013	0.022
Varieties									
BRRIdhan56	24.16	39.90	50.98	78.16	0.073	0.052	0.128	0.161	0.415
BRRIdhan57	24.08	47.39	48.59	79.89	0.062	0.052	0.118	0.177	0.409
BRRIdhan62	28.83	40.26	52.11	80.02	0.075	0.045	0.138	0.180	0.438
LSD _(.05)	1.298	2.872	NS	NS	0.004	0.004	0.008	0.013	0.022
Zinc × Variety									
Zn ₀ × V ₁	16.52	30.47	39.87	62.77	0.050	0.040	0.102	0.121	0.312
Zn ₁₀ × V ₁	24.80	38.73	50.07	81.07	0.079	0.053	0.136	0.175	0.444
Zn ₂₀ × V ₁	31.17	50.50	63.00	90.63	0.091	0.063	0.148	0.188	0.489
Zn ₀ × V ₂	16.27	39.47	37.03	69.27	0.041	0.042	0.089	0.150	0.322
Zn ₁₀ × V ₂	26.63	46.63	48.80	80.83	0.073	0.055	0.132	0.191	0.451
Zn ₂₀ × V ₂	29.33	56.07	59.93	89.57	0.072	0.059	0.134	0.191	0.456
Zn ₀ × V ₃	19.73	32.23	40.83	67.30	0.047	0.033	0.100	0.140	0.320
Zn ₁₀ × V ₃	26.90	39.63	53.10	82.10	0.070	0.044	0.139	0.186	0.440
Zn ₂₀ × V ₃	39.85	48.90	62.40	90.67	0.108	0.057	0.175	0.214	0.554
LSD _(.05)	2.25	NS	NS	NS	0.006	NS	0.015	NS	0.037
CV (%)	5.06	6.76	5.27	5.0	5.13	7.79	6.6	7.49	5.11

Table-5 Mean comparison of zinc fertilizer application on nitrogen partitioning in rice genotypes endosperm, bran, leaf and culm

ZnxGenotypes Interactions	Efficiency			
	Agronomic kg ha ⁻¹	Physiological kg kg ⁻¹	Apparent recovery %	Utilization kg kg ⁻¹
Zn ₀ V ₁				
Zn ₁₀ V ₁	18.54	36.13	13.1	47.27
Zn ₂₀ V ₁	5.75	14.67	8.8	13.48
Zn ₀ V ₂				
Zn ₁₀ V ₂	30.13	49.07	130	63.63
Zn ₂₀ V ₂	8.58	36.57	6.7	24.40
Zn ₀ V ₃				
Zn ₁₀ V ₃	28.23	43.09	12.0	52.46
Zn ₂₀ V ₃	25.97	47.48	11.7	54.96
LSD _(.05)	12.04	24.19	2.3	31.51
CV (%)	14.84	16.07	11.54	17.59

grains was higher as compared to straw, under all applied-treatments. These results are in agreement with findings of Takkar (1996).

Effect of zinc on phosphorus content and uptake

The highest P content in endosperm 0.145% was found at interaction of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ with BRR1 dhan 56 and the lowest of that 0.119% was obtained for interaction of control treatment in BRR1 dhan 62. The highest P content in bran 0.046% was found for interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 56 and the lowest of that 0.027% was obtained for interaction of control treatment in BRR1 dhan 56. The highest P content in leaf 0.06% was found at interaction of control treatment in BRR1 dhan 62 and the lowest of that 0.028% was obtained in interaction of control treatment in BRR1 dhan 57. The highest P content in culm 0.042% was found in interaction of control treatment in BRR1 dhan 56 and the lowest of that 0.017% was obtained in interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 57. The highest P uptake in endosperm 4.61 kg ha⁻¹ was found for interaction of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ with BRR1 dhan 56 and the lowest of that 2.83 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained in interaction of control treatment for BRR1 dhan 62. The highest P uptake in bran 0.574 kg ha⁻¹ was found at interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ with BRR1 dhan 56 and the lowest of that 0.348 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained for interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 57. The highest P uptake in leaf 1.46 kg ha⁻¹ was found for interaction of control treatment in BRR1 dhan 62 and the lowest of that 0.67 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained in interaction of control treatment for BRR1 dhan 57. The highest P uptake in culm was found at interaction of BRR1 dhan 62 of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ and the lowest of that 0.352 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained for interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 57. The highest total P uptake 6.79 kg ha⁻¹ was found for interaction of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ with BRR1 dhan 56 and the lowest of that 4.9 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained in interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 57 (Table 2). Phosphorus interacts with Zn in soil and reduces Zn translocation from roots to the shoots. The lowest value of 0.036% P content was recorded in treatment receiving 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ which might be due to the antagonistic effect of Zn on P uptake it was more pronounced in higher levels of zinc treatments. (Chaudhry et al., 1989) reported similar findings.

Effect of zinc on phosphorus content and uptake

The highest K content in endosperm 0.34% was found at interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 62 and the lowest of that 0.24% was obtained for interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 56. The highest K content in bran 0.27% was found for interaction of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 57 and the lowest of that 0.21% was obtained for interaction of control treatment in BRR1 dhan 56. The highest K content in leaf 0.75% was found in interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 62 and the lowest of that 0.58% was obtained in interaction of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 56. The highest K content in culm 0.99% was found in interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 62 and the lowest of that 0.71% was obtained in interaction of control treatment in BRR1 dhan 57. The highest K uptake in endosperm 9.28 kg ha⁻¹ was found for interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ with BRR1 dhan 62 and the lowest of that 6.71 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained in interaction of control treatment for BRR1 dhan 57. The highest K uptake in bran 3.37 kg ha⁻¹ was found for interaction of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ with BRR1 dhan 56 and the lowest of that 2.35 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained in interaction of control treatment for BRR1 dhan 62. The highest K uptake in leaf 21.16 kg ha⁻¹ was found for interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ with BRR1 dhan 62 and the lowest of that 13.53 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained in interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ for BRR1 dhan 56. The highest K uptakes in culm 23.42 kg ha⁻¹ was found in interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ with BRR1 dhan 62 and the lowest of that 15.14 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained in interaction of control treatment in BRR1 dhan 56. The highest K uptake 56.88 kg ha⁻¹ was found for interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 62 and the lowest of that 38.74 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained in interaction of control treatment in BRR1 dhan 56 (Table 3). These results are confirmation-findings of Iqbal et al., (2000), they reported that K concentration of both paddy and straw showed increasing trend with Zn fertilizer application.

Effect of zinc on zinc content and uptake

There is a statistically significant difference in zinc content (ppm) in endosperm among rice varieties. The highest Zn content in endosperm 28.83 ppm was obtained for BRR1 dhan 62 and the lowest of that 24.08 ppm was obtained for BRR1 dhan 57. The highest Zn content in bran was found for interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 57 (56.07 ppm) and the lowest of that 30.47 ppm was obtained for interaction of control treatment in BRR1 dhan 57. The highest Zn content in leaf 63 ppm was found in interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 62 and the lowest of that 37.03 ppm was obtained in interaction of control treatment in BRR1 dhan 57. The highest Zn content in culm 90.67 ppm was found in interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 62 and the lowest of that 62.77 ppm was obtained in interaction of control treatment in BRR1 dhan 57. Genotypic variation in rice grain Zn concentration might be due to the difference in physiological processes determining Zn accumulation in grains (Gao et al., 2012). The increase in the zinc content in grain and straw might be due to the presence of increased amount of Zn in soil solution by the application of zinc that facilitated greater absorption. Wissuwa et al., (2008) also showed a significant variation in grain Zn concentration (e.g., from 8 to 47 mg kg⁻¹) for a given rice genotype when grown on different soil types. These results indicate that environmental conditions have significant impact on grain Zn concentrations. The highest Zn uptake in endosperm 0.108 kg ha⁻¹ was found for interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ with BRR1 dhan 62 and the lowest of

that 0.041 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained in interaction of control treatment for BRR1 dhan 57. The highest Zn uptake in bran 0.063 kg ha⁻¹ was found for interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ with BRR1 dhan 57 and the lowest of that 0.033 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained in interaction of control treatment for BRR1 dhan 62. The highest Zn uptake in leaf 0.175 kg ha⁻¹ was found for interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ with BRR1 dhan 62 and the lowest of that 0.089 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained in interaction of control treatment for BRR1 dhan 57. The highest Zn uptake in culm 0.191 kg ha⁻¹ was found in interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ with BRR1 dhan 57 and the lowest of that 0.121 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained in interaction of control treatment in BRR1 dhan 56. The highest total Zn uptake 0.554 kg ha⁻¹ was found for interaction of 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 62 and the lowest of that 0.312 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained in interaction of control treatment in BRR1 dhan 56 (Table 4). The data further showed that application of zinc increased the zinc contents of plant which might be owing to more vigour of plants and greater root development which favored the uptake of element due to increased Zn application. Similar results were found by (Sanzoet al., 1989), (Singh et al., 1996) and (Srivastava et al., 1999).

Zinc use efficiency

Result revealed significant effects of the AZnE efficiency 30.13 was found for interaction of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ with BRR1 dhan 57 and the lowest of that 8.58 was obtained for interaction of control treatment for BRR1 dhan 57. The highest PZnE efficiency 49.07 was found for interaction of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ with BRR1 dhan 57 and the lowest of that 36.57 was obtained for interaction of control treatment for BRR1 dhan 57. The highest ARZn Efficiency 1.31 was found in interaction of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 56 and the lowest of that 0.67 was obtained for interaction of control treatment in BRR1 dhan 57. The highest UE efficiency 63.63 was found in interaction of 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 56 and the lowest of that 24.40 was obtained for interaction of control treatment for Binadhan-11 (Table 5). Agronomic, physiological and agro-physiological efficiencies apparent Zn recovery and Zn utilization efficiency decreased significantly with Zn levels. This relationship clearly demonstrated the importance of ZnUE to the rice yield with special emphasis on physiological and agro-physiological efficiency which accounted for the maximum variation. Higher ZnUE at lower Zn level was reported by (Fageria et al., 2003) in rice.

CONCLUSION

The total N uptake varied from 70.86 kg ha⁻¹ to 106.59 kg ha⁻¹, total P uptake from 4.904 kg ha⁻¹ to 6.792 kg ha⁻¹, K uptake from 38.74 kg ha⁻¹ to 56.88 kg ha⁻¹ and Zn uptake from 0.312 kg ha⁻¹ to 0.554 kg ha⁻¹ across the treatments. The application of different doses of zinc fertilizer exerted significant effect on Zn content in endosperm in rice varieties rice varieties, BRR1 dhan 56, BRR1 dhan 57 and BRR1 dhan 62. The highest Zn content in endosperm (39.85 ppm) was found at 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 62 and the lowest of 16.27 ppm was obtained at 0 kg Zn ha⁻¹ in BRR1 dhan 57. The highest agronomic, physiological, apparent recovery and utilization efficiency were recorded at 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ and the lowest at 20 kg Zn ha⁻¹. Among three rice varieties tested, the variety BRR1 dhan 62 showed high zinc uptake ability and high grain zinc content.

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